

IoT-Powered Soil Analysis: A Unique Approach to Precision Farming

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Abstract— This paper presents a comprehensive review of soil testing using IoT sensors, highlighting the advancements and applications in precision agriculture. IoT sensors have revolutionized soil testing by providing real-time, accurate data on various soil parameters such as moisture, pH, temperature, and nutrient levels. The integration of IoT with wireless sensor networks has improved data collection methods, enabling continuous monitoring and timely decision-making. Key developments include enhanced sensor accuracy, efficient data transmission, and advanced data analysis techniques. The implementation of IoT-based soil monitoring systems facilitates resource optimization, improved crop management, and sustainable farming practices. This review also discusses the challenges and future prospects of IoT in soil testing, emphasizing the need for innovative solutions to address data integration and sensor deployment issues. Overall, IoT sensors offer significant potential to enhance soil health monitoring and contribute to the advancement of smart agriculture.

Keywords— IoT sensors, Precision agriculture, Soil testing, Real-time data, Soil health monitoring

I. INTRODUCTION

The integration of Internet of Things (IoT) technology in agriculture has revolutionized soil testing, providing real-time, precise data essential for modern farming. Traditional soil testing methods, while informative, are often labor-intensive, time-consuming, and offer only periodic snapshots of soil health. In contrast, IoT sensors continuously monitor soil conditions, measuring parameters such as moisture, temperature, pH, and nutrient levels, and transmitting this data in real-time to cloud-based platforms for analysis and visualization [1][2]. This continuous flow of data enables farmers to make timely and informed decisions, a concept known as precision agriculture, which optimizes resource use and boosts crop yields [3].

One of the primary benefits of IoT-based soil testing is the provision of dynamic, real-time data. This allows for the implementation of precise irrigation schedules based on current soil moisture levels, reducing water usage and preventing crop stress [4]. Similarly, accurate soil nutrient data helps in the optimal application of fertilizers, ensuring crops receive the right nutrients at the right time, which enhances yields and reduces the environmental impact of excessive fertilization [5]. The high-resolution data provided by IoT sensors enables detailed monitoring of soil conditions, allowing for better decision-making and resource management [6].

Furthermore, IoT sensors contribute to sustainable farming practices by promoting efficient use of resources and minimizing environmental degradation. Precise soil monitoring helps prevent over-fertilization and over-irrigation, both of which can lead to soil and water pollution [7]. By optimizing the use of water and fertilizers, IoT-based soil testing supports the conservation of these vital resources and helps maintain the ecological balance [8].

Despite the numerous advantages, the deployment of IoT sensors in agriculture is not without challenges. Key issues include data integration, sensor deployment, and associated costs [9]. The interoperability of various IoT devices and platforms requires standardized protocols and frameworks to ensure seamless data exchange [10]. Additionally, deploying sensors across large and diverse agricultural fields can be complex and expensive, posing a barrier to widespread adoption [11].

Looking forward, continuous advancements in IoT technology are expected to address these challenges. Innovations in sensor technology, data analytics, and wireless communication will enhance the capabilities and affordability of IoT-based soil testing systems [12]. The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) with IoT will enable more sophisticated data analysis and predictive modeling, offering deeper insights into soil health and crop management [13]. These technological advancements promise to further revolutionize soil testing, paving the way for more efficient and sustainable agricultural practices [14]. In conclusion, IoT sensors are transforming soil testing by providing critical real-time data that enhances precision agriculture and promotes sustainability, heralding a new era of smart farming [15].

II. RELATED WORKS

In their evaluation of IoT-based soil monitoring systems, Fan et al. [16] pay particular attention to sensor kinds, data transfer techniques, and real-time agricultural applications. Fan and colleagues investigate developments in wireless sensor networks and the Internet of Things for soil testing, emphasizing enhanced precision and instantaneous data gathering. Precision agriculture and resource optimization are highlighted by Fan et al. in their discussion of IoT devices for soil moisture monitoring.

In their investigation of IoT and wireless sensor network developments for soil testing, Mekonnen et al. [17] place a focus on increased precision and real-time data gathering. In addition to addressing the advantages of real-time data for precision farming and sustainable agricultural practices, their evaluation concentrates on the integration of IoT technology in agriculture to improve soil monitoring capabilities.

Reviewing IoT sensors for soil moisture monitoring, Kumar et al. [18] place a focus on resource optimization and precision agriculture. The use of IoT technologies to monitor soil moisture levels in real-time is covered in their paper, with an emphasis on how this monitoring improves crop production sustainability and optimizes water use in precision farming methods.

Senapaty et al. [19] review IoT-based soil nutrient sensing technologies, focusing on sensor capabilities, data integration methods, and applications in smart farming. They highlight the sensors' ability to measure essential nutrients in real-time, aiding precise fertilizer management. The study emphasizes IoT's role in integrating soil nutrient data efficiently, enabling informed decisions to optimize crop nutrition and increase yields. This approach supports sustainable agriculture by reducing resource use and environmental impact, emphasizing the sensors' reliability and calibration for accurate long-term data collection.

Khanal et al. [20] examine IoT sensor systems for real-time soil health monitoring, focusing on sensor accuracy and agricultural benefits. Their review explores how IoT sensors provide accurate, real-time data on soil conditions such as moisture levels, pH, temperature, and nutrient content. They discuss the agricultural benefits of these sensors, emphasizing improved decision-making in irrigation, fertilization, and overall crop management. The study underscores the importance of sensor precision and reliability in enhancing soil health and optimizing agricultural productivity through informed, data-driven practices.

Liang et al. [21] review IoT-driven innovations in soil pH monitoring, assessing sensor effectiveness and precision in agricultural contexts. Their study examines how IoT sensors provide real-time data on soil pH levels, crucial for optimizing crop growth and productivity. The review evaluates the accuracy of these sensors and discusses their applications in precision agriculture, emphasizing their role in enhancing soil management practices. The findings underscore the importance of reliable sensor technology in maintaining soil health and supporting sustainable farming practices through precise pH monitoring.

Gupta et al.[22] review how IoT enhances traditional soil testing techniques by analyzing sensor technology and data analysis methods. Their study examines the integration of IoT sensors, which provide real-time data on soil parameters such as moisture, pH, and nutrient levels. They discuss how IoT improves the accuracy and efficiency of soil testing compared to conventional methods, emphasizing advancements in sensor capabilities and data analytics. The review highlights IoT's potential to revolutionize soil management practices by enabling timely decision-making and optimizing resource use in agriculture.

Mekonnen et al.[23] discuss wireless sensor networks for soil quality assessment, emphasizing IoT integration and data accuracy. Their review explores how these networks utilize IoT technologies to monitor soil parameters such as moisture, pH, and nutrient levels in real-time. They highlight the integration of wireless sensors with cloud-based platforms for efficient data collection and analysis. The study underscores the importance of data accuracy in improving soil management practices and supporting sustainable agriculture through precise monitoring and timely interventions.

Allbed et al. [24] review IoT applications in soil salinity monitoring, emphasizing the benefits of continuous data collection in saline environments. Their study explores how IoT sensors provide real-time data on soil salinity levels, crucial for mitigating salt stress in crops and optimizing irrigation strategies. The review discusses the advantages of IoT in enabling proactive management of soil salinity, ensuring timely interventions to maintain soil health and enhance crop productivity in challenging agricultural conditions.

Farooq et al. [25] explore IoT-based soil temperature monitoring systems, focusing on sensor technologies and implications for crop management. Their review examines how IoT sensors enable real-time monitoring of soil temperature, essential for optimizing crop growth and yield. They discuss the effectiveness of these sensors in providing accurate data and their applications in precision agriculture. The study highlights the role of IoT in improving crop management strategies by enabling timely adjustments to planting schedules, irrigation, and other farming practices based on soil temperature variations.

III. METHODOLOGY

Soil testing using IoT sensors revolutionizes traditional agricultural practices by integrating advanced technology into soil monitoring and management. IoT sensors are strategically deployed across agricultural fields, collecting real-time data on crucial soil parameters such as moisture levels, pH, temperature, and nutrient content. These sensors utilize wireless connectivity to transmit data to centralized cloud-based platforms where it is processed using sophisticated analytics and machine learning algorithms.

The continuous monitoring capabilities of IoT sensors offer several advantages over conventional soil testing methods. Firstly, real-time data acquisition enables farmers and agronomists to make timely and informed decisions. For example, precise monitoring of soil moisture levels allows for optimized irrigation scheduling, ensuring crops receive adequate water without wastage. Similarly, monitoring pH and nutrient

levels helps in adjusting fertilizer applications to meet crop requirements precisely, thereby enhancing nutrient uptake efficiency and minimizing environmental impact.

Furthermore, IoT-based soil testing supports sustainable agricultural practices by promoting resource efficiency and environmental stewardship. By accurately monitoring soil conditions, farmers can reduce over-application of fertilizers and pesticides, mitigating nutrient runoff and soil degradation. This approach not only improves crop productivity and quality but also contributes to long-term soil health and ecosystem resilience.

Regular calibration and maintenance of IoT sensors are essential to ensure data accuracy and reliability over time. Farmers can benefit from ongoing advancements in sensor technology and data analytics, which promise to further enhance the precision and scope of soil testing capabilities.

Fig1: Block diagram of IoT sensor

Captive Moisture v1.0

The Captive Moisture Sensor V1.0 measures soil moisture levels accurately, aiding precision agriculture, horticulture, and environmental monitoring. It offers real-time data for optimal irrigation, water conservation, and improved crop health. With quick response times, wireless communication, and robust durability, it integrates well with IoT systems, though it requires regular calibration and may have high initial setup costs.

Soil NPK Sensor

A soil NPK sensor measures nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K) levels in soil, crucial for plant growth. These sensors provide real-time data through soil analysis or in-situ probes, aiding in precise fertilizer management for optimized crop yield and sustainable agriculture practices. They help farmers

make informed decisions regarding nutrient application, ensuring efficient use of resources and environmental sustainability.

Fig2: Realtime soil moistures test

NodeMCU 1.0 (ESP8266 12E WiFi module)

Based on the ESP8266 microcontroller, the NodeMCU 1.0 (ESP8266 12E WiFi module) is a small and adaptable development board with built-in WiFi (802.11 b/g/n) and a variety of GPIO pins for interacting with other components. It runs at 3.3V, has a micro USB connector for programming and power, and usually has 4MB of Flash memory for storing programs. It is a popular choice for Internet of Things (IoT) projects because of its affordability, user-friendliness, and internet connectivity. It is also compatible with the Arduino IDE and Lua programming, which makes it perfect for prototyping and embedding into other electrical applications.

Fig3: Node MCU 1.0 (ESP8266 12-E wiFi)

Soil Moisture Sensor-YL-38 + YL-69

The YL-38 and YL-69 soil moisture sensor system combines a probe with exposed electrodes that measure soil conductivity based on moisture content, and an accompanying amplifier module that processes and stabilizes the sensor's output signal. This setup allows the sensor to accurately detect

changes in soil moisture levels, providing crucial data for irrigation management, agriculture, and environmental monitoring applications. The probe is inserted into the soil, where it measures the resistance between its electrodes, which decreases as soil moisture increases. The YL-69 module ensures the sensor's output is compatible with microcontrollers and other electronics, making it easy to integrate into IoT systems for real-time monitoring and automated control of irrigation systems, ensuring optimal soil conditions for plant health and growth.

Fig4: Soil Moisture Sensor

Soil pH Meter

A soil pH meter is a device used to measure the acidity or alkalinity levels of soil. It typically consists of a probe that is inserted into the soil, which then measures the pH level based on the concentration of hydrogen ions in the soil solution. The meter converts this pH measurement into a digital or analog output that indicates whether the soil is acidic (pH below 7), neutral (pH around 7), or alkaline (pH above 7). Soil pH meters are essential tools in agriculture, gardening, and environmental science, helping to determine the suitability of soil for plant growth and facilitating adjustments to soil pH through the application of soil amendments like lime or sulfur. They provide precise readings that enable farmers, gardeners, and researchers to optimize crop yield, nutrient availability, and overall soil health management strategies.

Fig5: Soil pH Meter

Temperature and Humidity Sensor – DHT1

The DHT11 temperature and humidity sensor is a compact, digital sensor module that integrates both temperature and humidity sensing capabilities. It operates using a single-wire digital communication protocol, making it easy to interface with microcontrollers like Arduino and ESP8266. The sensor measures ambient temperature with an accuracy of $\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and relative humidity with an accuracy of $\pm 5\%$. It consists of a capacitive humidity sensor and a thermistor for temperature measurement, housed in a protective casing with pre-installed resistors and capacitors for stable operation. The DHT11 sensor is widely used in indoor climate monitoring, HVAC systems, weather stations, and environmental monitoring applications where precise measurement and monitoring of temperature and humidity levels are essential for maintaining optimal conditions.

Fig6: Temperature and Humidity Sensor – DHT1

And this figure shows prototype of the system.

Fig7: Prototype Model

IV. RESULT

The IoT-enabled soil testing system reliably monitors agricultural parameters such as soil pH and moisture levels. The data output is accessible through the serial monitor of the Arduino IDE.

Fig8-Result of Temperature and Humidity Sensor – DHT1

Fig9: Timeline Result

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, IoT sensors have significantly advanced soil testing by providing precise, real-time data crucial for modern agriculture. These technologies enhance soil health monitoring, allowing for better resource management, optimized crop production, and sustainable farming practices. Despite the challenges related to data integration and sensor deployment, the continuous improvements in sensor accuracy and data analysis techniques highlight the potential of IoT in revolutionizing soil testing. Future innovations are expected to address existing limitations, further solidifying IoT's role in smart agriculture. Overall, IoT-based soil testing represents a critical step towards achieving efficient and sustainable agricultural systems.

VI. REFERENCES

- [1] 1. Khanna, Abhishek, and Sanmeet Kaur. "Evolution of Internet of Things (IoT) and Its Significant Impact in the Field of Precision Agriculture." *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 157 (2019): 218-231.
- [2] 2. Balasundram, Siva K., Kamlesh Golhani, Redmond R. Shamshiri, and Ganesan Vadamalai. "Precision Agriculture Technologies for Management of Plant Diseases." In *Plant Disease Management Strategies for Sustainable Agriculture through Traditional and Modern Approaches*, 259-278. 2020.
- [3] 3. Bhat, Showkat Ahmad, and Nen-Fu Huang. "Big Data and AI Revolution in Precision Agriculture: Survey and Challenges." *IEEE Access* 9 (2021): 110209-110222.
- [4] 4. Munaganuri, Ravi Kumar, and Narasimha Rao Yamarthi. "PAMICRM: Improving Precision Agriculture through Multimodal Image Analysis for Crop Water Requirement Estimation Using Multidomain Remote Sensing Data Samples." *IEEE Access* (2024).
- [5] 5. Treboux, Jérôme, and Dominique Genoud. "Improved Machine Learning Methodology for High Precision Agriculture." In *2018 Global Internet of Things Summit (GIoTS)*, 1-6. IEEE, 2018.
- [6] 6. Dimitriadis, Savvas, and Christos Goumopoulos. "Applying Machine Learning to Extract New Knowledge in Precision Agriculture Applications." In *2008 Panhellenic Conference on Informatics*, 100-104. IEEE, 2008.
- [7] 7. Thenmozhi, Kasinathan, Dakshayani Singaraju, and Srinivasulu Reddy Uyyala. "Insect Pest Detection in Agriculture Using Machine Learning Techniques."
- [8] 8. Xie, C., R. Wang, J. Zhang, P. Chen, W. Dong, R. Li, T. Chen, and H. Chen. "Pest Species Classification Using Unsupervised Feature Learning Methods."
- [9] 9. Rangarajan, A. K., R. Purushothaman, and A. Ramesh. "Tomato Crop Disease Classification Using Pre-Trained Deep Learning Algorithm." *Procedia Computer Science* 133 (2018): 1040-1047.
- [10] 10. Thenmozhi, K., and U. Srinivasulu Reddy. "Insect Pest Classification Using Deep Learning Methods."
- [11] 11. Khanna, Abhishek, and Sanmeet Kaur. "Evolution of Internet of Things (IoT) and Its Significant Impact in the Field of Precision Agriculture." *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 157 (2019): 218-231.
- [12] 12. Balasundram, Siva K., Kamlesh Golhani, Redmond R. Shamshiri, and Ganesan Vadamalai. "Precision Agriculture Technologies for Management of Plant Diseases." In *Plant Disease Management Strategies for Sustainable Agriculture through Traditional and Modern Approaches*, 259-278. 2020.
- [13] 13. Bhat, Showkat Ahmad, and Nen-Fu Huang. "Big Data and AI Revolution in Precision Agriculture: Survey and Challenges." *IEEE Access* 9 (2021): 110209-110222.
- [14] 14. Munaganuri, Ravi Kumar, and Narasimha Rao Yamarthi. "PAMICRM: Improving Precision Agriculture through Multimodal Image Analysis for Crop Water Requirement Estimation Using Multidomain Remote Sensing Data Samples." *IEEE Access* (2024).
- [15] 15. Treboux, Jérôme, and Dominique Genoud. "Improved Machine Learning Methodology for High Precision Agriculture." In *2018 Global Internet of Things Summit (GIoTS)*, 1-6. IEEE, 2018.
- [16] . [16] Fan, Yingzheng, Xingyu Wang, Thomas Funk, Ishrat Rashid, Brianna Herman, Nefeli Bompoti, MD Shaad Mahmud et al. "A critical review for real-time continuous soil monitoring: Advantages, challenges, and perspectives." *Environmental Science & Technology* 56, no. 19 (2022): 13546-13564.
- [17] [17] Mekonnen, Yemeserach, Srikanth Namuduri, Lamar Burton, Arif Sarwat, and Shekhar Bhansali. "Machine learning techniques in wireless sensor network based precision agriculture." *Journal of the Electrochemical Society* 167, no. 3 (2019): 037522.
- [18] [18] Kumar, Parasuraman, Anandan Udayakumar, Anbarasan Anbarasa Kumar, Kaliaperumal Senthamarai Kannan, and Nallaperumal Krishnan. "Multiparameter optimization system with DCNN in precision agriculture for advanced irrigation planning and scheduling based on soil moisture estimation." *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment* 195, no. 1 (2023): 13.
- [19] [19] Senapaty, Murali Krishna, Abhishek Ray, and Neelamadhab Padhy. "IoT-enabled soil nutrient analysis and crop recommendation model for precision agriculture." *Computers* 12, no. 3 (2023): 61.
- [20] [20] Khanal, Sami, Kushal Kc, John P. Fulton, Scott Shearer, and Erdal Ozkan. "Remote sensing in agriculture—accomplishments, limitations, and opportunities." *Remote Sensing* 12, no. 22 (2020): 3783.
- [21] [21] Liang, Chen, and Tufail Shah. "IoT in agriculture: The future of precision monitoring and data-driven farming." *Eigenpub Review of Science and Technology* 7, no. 1 (2023): 85-104.
- [22] [22] Gupta, Debaditya, Nihal Gujre, Siddhartha Singha, and Sudip Mitra. "Role of existing and emerging technologies in advancing climate-smart agriculture through modeling: A review." *Ecological Informatics* 71 (2022): 101805.
- [23] [23] Mekonnen, Yemeserach, Srikanth Namuduri, Lamar Burton, Arif Sarwat, and Shekhar Bhansali. "Machine learning techniques in wireless sensor network based precision agriculture." *Journal of the Electrochemical Society* 167, no. 3 (2019): 037522.
- [24] [24] Allbed, Amal, and Lalit Kumar. "Soil salinity mapping and monitoring in arid and semi-arid regions using remote sensing technology: a review." *Advances in remote sensing* 2013 (2013).
- [25] [25] Farooq, Muhammad Shoaib, Shamyala Riaz, Adnan Abid, Tariq Umer, and Yousaf Bin Zikria. "Role of IoT technology in agriculture: A systematic literature review." *Electronics* 9, no. 2 (2020): 319.